

THE USAGE OF SPACED REPETITION TECHNIQUE TO CHILDREN'S
MEMORIZATION OF NEW VOCABULARY

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Abstract

The Spaced Repetition Technique (SRT) is a highly effective method for enhancing memory retention and learning efficiency, particularly in children learning new vocabulary. This article explores the practical applications and benefits of SRT in educational settings. By utilizing tools such as flashcards and digital apps, educators and parents can implement structured review sessions that reinforce learning at optimal intervals. Personalized learning plans and adaptive technologies further tailor the SRT approach to individual needs, ensuring each child receives the appropriate reinforcement. Additionally, incorporating SRT into classroom activities, after-school programs, and home study routines can significantly boost motivation, engagement, and long-term retention. The article highlights the versatility and adaptability of SRT, making it an invaluable tool for improving academic outcomes and fostering lifelong learning habits in children.

Keywords: Spaced Repetition Technique, Memory Retention, Vocabulary Acquisition, Educational Tools, Flashcards, Digital Learning Apps, Personalized Learning, Adaptive Learning Technologies, Long-Term Retention, Learning Efficiency

As everyone knows, many techniques are used to learn a new language and remember new words in it. We will consider the use of spaced repetition technique to effectively organize this situation especially in children.

What is Spaced Repetition Technique (SRT)?

The Spaced Repetition Technique (SRT) is a learning method designed to enhance memory retention by strategically spacing out review sessions of learned material over increasing intervals of time. This technique is grounded in the psychological research of Hermann Ebbinghaus, a pioneer in the study of memory and forgetting. Hermann Ebbinghaus's experiments in the late 19th century led to the development of the forgetting curve, which illustrates how information is lost over time if there is no attempt to retain it. His research showed that the most significant drop in retention happens soon after learning, but subsequent reviews can help strengthen memory and slow the rate of forgetting. This concept laid the foundation for spaced repetition. How Spaced Repetition Works:

1. **Initial Learning Phase:** New information is introduced and learned.
2. **First Review:** The material is reviewed shortly after the initial learning session, ideally within 24 hours. This quick review helps transfer the information from short-term to long-term memory.
3. **Subsequent Reviews:** Reviews are spaced out over progressively longer intervals (e.g., one day, three days, one week, two weeks, one month). Each review reinforces the memory, making it less likely to be forgotten.

Forgetting Curve: Ebbinghaus's forgetting curve shows that without review, we forget information quickly. Spaced repetition counters this by reintroducing the material just as we are about to forget it, which strengthens the memory.

Spacing Effect: This principle states that learning is more effective when study sessions are spaced out over time, rather than crammed into a short period (massed practice). Spacing allows the brain to process and consolidate information more effectively. **Testing Effect:** Actively recalling information (retrieval practice) during spaced intervals strengthens memory and understanding more than passive review. **Flashcards:** One of the most common tools for SRT is flashcards. Digital flashcard apps like Anki and Quizlet use algorithms to determine optimal review intervals for each card based on the

user's performance. **Educational Software:** Various educational platforms integrate spaced repetition into their curricula, especially for language learning (e.g., Duolingo, Memrise). **Personal Study Plans:** Students and educators can manually incorporate spaced repetition into their study schedules by planning review sessions at increasing intervals. **Long-Term Retention:** By regularly reviewing material over time, learners can achieve better long-term retention compared to cramming.

1. **Efficiency:** Spaced repetition allows for efficient use of study time, focusing on material just before it is forgotten, thus reducing the total time needed for studying.
2. **Adaptability:** The technique can be adapted to various subjects and learners, making it versatile for different educational contexts.
3. **Motivation:** Seeing progress and retention of information can boost motivation and confidence in learners.

The Spaced Repetition Technique is a powerful method grounded in cognitive psychology that optimizes the learning process by strategically spacing review sessions. Its application across various fields and its adaptability to individual learning needs make it an invaluable tool for enhancing memory retention and learning efficiency.

Benefits of SRT for Children

The Spaced Repetition Technique (SRT) offers significant benefits for children by enhancing their memory retention and learning efficiency. It helps children memorize new vocabulary more effectively and retain it in their long-term memory through strategically timed review sessions. This method boosts motivation by allowing children to see quick progress and reinforces learning with consistent practice. Additionally, SRT's flexibility allows it to be tailored to individual learning needs, making it suitable for diverse learners. By integrating SRT into their study routines, children can achieve better academic outcomes with less effort

and more lasting results. The Spaced Repetition Technique (SRT) is a highly effective educational tool that offers numerous benefits for children, particularly in the realm of vocabulary acquisition and memory retention. One of the primary advantages of SRT is its ability to enhance long-term retention of information. By spacing out review sessions over increasing intervals, SRT leverages the psychological principle known as the spacing effect, which suggests that information is more effectively retained when learning sessions are distributed over time. This is particularly beneficial for children, as their developing brains are highly receptive to structured learning techniques that reinforce information at optimal intervals. Through SRT, children can more efficiently encode new vocabulary into their long-term memory, reducing the cognitive load during subsequent learning sessions and making the retrieval of information more automatic and less effortful. Furthermore, SRT significantly boosts motivation and engagement in learning. The structured nature of SRT, with its predictable review sessions, provides children with a clear framework and tangible progress markers. This consistent reinforcement helps build confidence as children witness their own improvement, fostering a positive feedback loop that encourages continued effort and persistence. The motivational benefits of SRT are amplified by the frequent successes children experience as they successfully recall previously learned material, which can be especially encouraging for young learners who might otherwise become discouraged by the challenges of mastering new vocabulary. Additionally, SRT offers a high degree of adaptability, making it suitable for a wide range of learning environments and individual needs. It can be easily integrated into various educational settings, from traditional classrooms to homeschooling environments, and can be customized to accommodate the unique learning paces and preferences of individual children. This adaptability extends to the use of different learning tools and resources, such as flashcards, digital apps, and interactive games, all of which can be tailored to incorporate SRT principles.

By providing a flexible and personalized learning experience, SRT ensures that each child can benefit from the technique, regardless of their specific learning style or needs. Moreover, the efficiency of SRT cannot be overstated. By focusing on the review of information just as it is about to be forgotten, SRT minimizes the amount of time children need to spend on rote memorization. This targeted approach not only enhances the effectiveness of study sessions but also frees up time for children to engage in other educational activities and pursuits. In an era where children are often juggling multiple academic and extracurricular commitments, the time-saving aspect of SRT is a significant advantage, allowing them to achieve better academic outcomes with less overall effort. In conclusion, the Spaced Repetition Technique offers a multitude of benefits for children, making it an invaluable tool in the realm of education. Its ability to enhance long-term retention, boost motivation, and provide a highly adaptable and efficient learning strategy makes it particularly well-suited for young learners. By incorporating SRT into their study routines, children can achieve significant improvements in vocabulary acquisition and overall academic performance, setting a strong foundation for lifelong learning and success.

Practical Application of SRT

The practical application of the Spaced Repetition Technique (SRT) in educational settings, especially for children, is a powerful approach that enhances learning efficiency and long-term retention of new vocabulary and concepts. Implementing SRT can be done through various tools and strategies that fit seamlessly into the daily routines of both students and educators. One of the most common and effective tools for SRT is the use of flashcards. Traditional physical flashcards have been a staple in education for years, but with advancements in technology, digital flashcards have become increasingly popular. Apps such as Anki, Quizlet, and Memrise utilize algorithms that automatically schedule review sessions at optimal intervals, ensuring that children review material just before they are likely

to forget it. These apps often incorporate multimedia elements such as images, audio, and interactive features, which cater to different learning styles and make the learning process more engaging for children. In addition to flashcards, educators can incorporate SRT into classroom activities and lesson plans. Teachers can create structured review sessions that align with the principles of spaced repetition, ensuring that new vocabulary and concepts are revisited at increasing intervals. For example, after introducing a new set of vocabulary words, a teacher might schedule brief review sessions the next day, then three days later, a week later, and so on. This structured approach not only reinforces the material but also helps students develop a habit of regular review, which is crucial for long-term retention. Interactive classroom activities such as games, quizzes, and group discussions can be designed to incorporate spaced repetition, making the review process more dynamic and enjoyable for students. Another practical application of SRT is through personalized learning plans. Given the diverse learning needs and paces of individual students, personalized learning plans can be developed to tailor the SRT schedule to each child's unique needs. This can involve the use of adaptive learning technologies that monitor a student's progress and adjust the review intervals accordingly. For instance, if a child is struggling with certain vocabulary words, the system can shorten the intervals between reviews for those specific words, while lengthening the intervals for words the child has already mastered. This level of customization ensures that each student receives the appropriate amount of reinforcement needed to solidify their understanding and memory of the material. Moreover, parents can play a significant role in the practical application of SRT at home. By understanding the principles of spaced repetition, parents can help their children establish effective study habits. They can assist in setting up regular review schedules, using tools such as flashcards or digital apps, and creating a supportive learning environment that encourages consistent practice. Additionally, parents can engage in activities that naturally

incorporate spaced repetition, such as reading books together, playing educational games, or having regular conversations that include newly learned vocabulary. These activities not only reinforce learning but also make the process more enjoyable and relevant to the child's daily life. Furthermore, integrating SRT into after-school programs and tutoring sessions can provide additional support for children who need extra help with their studies. Tutors and program coordinators can design activities and review sessions based on the principles of spaced repetition, ensuring that the material is revisited at optimal intervals. This supplemental support can be particularly beneficial for children who may need more individualized attention or who are working to overcome specific learning challenges. In summary, the practical application of the Spaced Repetition Technique in children's education involves a multifaceted approach that includes the use of digital and physical flashcards, structured classroom activities, personalized learning plans, parental involvement, and additional support through after-school programs and tutoring. By incorporating SRT into these various aspects of a child's educational experience, we can enhance their ability to retain new vocabulary and concepts, making learning more efficient, effective, and enjoyable.

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